

Factors Influencing Online Education in Undergraduate Program during COVID-19 Pandemic Using Data Mining Techniques

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Abstract: Every educational institution makes an effort to boost the academic performance of its students since doing so contributes to an improvement in the quality of education as a whole. Educational Data Mining (EDM) is a fast-trending study area that employs the essence of Data Mining (DM) techniques to assist academic institutions in deciding critical information on student satisfaction. Because the variables that make up a satisfaction model may have a considerable influence on the accuracy of its prediction, the usefulness of the Student Satisfaction Level (SSL) model is studied in further detail here employing factors. A dataset was first collected using an online poll that asked students about their experiences with OL courses on related topics. Finding the EDM white zone and red zone factors using RStudio, Minitab, SPSS and other software those may be accomplished with the use of this dataset. In this section, we will examine the elements that positively impact online education, as well as the ones that need to be addressed in order for students to be able to adjust to online learning in a happy and successful manner. This dataset has the potential to be used in EDM to identify red zone characteristics. We're going to take a look at some of the factors that have a good impact on online education, as well as some of the factors that need to be addressed in order for students to make a smooth transition to online learning the accuracy of this model is 86.34 percent, which indicates that providing education over the internet is successful.

Keywords: Educational Data Mining (EDM), COVID-19, Online Learning (OL), Factors, Student Satisfaction Level (SSL).

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the SARS-CoV-2 virus is the infectious agent that causes Coronavirus illness (COVID-19). The majority of persons who get the virus will suffer from a respiratory disease that is either mild or moderate in severity, and they will recover without the need for any specialized therapy. On the other hand, some of them will get very sick and call for medical assistance. People who are older and those who already have a preexisting medical condition, such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, chronic respiratory disease, or cancer, have a greater risk of developing a severe illness. At any age, someone who has COVID-19 infection has the potential to get very ill or perhaps die [1].

Despite the fact that COVID-19 is rapidly spreading around the globe, numerous governments have been forced to self-impose quarantines in an effort to halt the progression of the virus. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization, at least 138 nations have discontinued the operation of their educational institutions. The suspension of these schools has had a substantial influence on children's learning, and the closure of schools for extended periods of time will make existing educational inequities much worse [2-5]. Educational differences will have an impact on all levels of geography, including regions, cities, and rural areas. The road of educational progress for the future will

consist of students attempting to gain academic judgment. There is a reasonable expectation that this will provide a window of opportunity for the expansion of online educational offerings. We will make advantage of this opportunity to establish the degree of contentment that people in Bangladesh have with regards to their online educational opportunities. After the breakout of COVID-19 [6-12], the sector that hampers a lot that is education sector. As education is the backbone of nation so it should not be stopped for fulfilling this basic need online education system approach. But educational organizations are facing so many unpleasant experiences on this issue. After studying so many related works, it seems that some specific factors need to find for adaptability with online education.

2. Methodology

2.1 Proposed Model

We will first use the null hypothesis as a guide. It is necessary for us to determine the Z region. Conducting data analysis using the T test, as well as determining the P value and Z value for each variable. Then, in accordance with the null hypothesis, the Z values need to be determined by using the Z area. In accordance with the Z area that was projected, we shall classify Z values into either the “White zone” or the “Red Zone.” The model organizes the many approaches to decision-making. In the process of prediction, DT, Nave Bayes, and SVM are all applied. In order for us to successfully do this work, we need to complete the following steps:

1. Problem definition and objective structuring: The data set will include both independent variables and a dependent variable. If we want to determine whether or not one of the independent variables has a major influence on the variable that is being measured, we have to look at all of them. As a consequence of this, it is necessary for us to identify the characteristics that contribute to student happiness. These characteristics may be related to age, gender, family financial conditions, [13] parental educational credentials, or other aspects of the student’s life. After that, we will make use of the data to attempt to construct a model that can anticipate the level of enjoyment experienced by the students. In addition to this method, we will evaluate the accuracy using a Decision Tree.
2. Data collection [14] and comprehension process: In order to gather data, we will need to design a questionnaire that both identifies the most important aspects of the problem and provides the Class Prediction (the target class). It is doable to send the survey to the students through email and then request that they complete it out. This is how we will get the training data set, which will ultimately provide us the Class that we are looking for.
3. Data Preparation [15-18] and Pre-Processing: After the method for collecting questionnaires has been finished, the next stage, which is data preparation, will start. The information will then be analyzed and altered in Excel sheets when it has been put into those spreadsheets. In addition, a few of the characteristics call for the conversion of numeric data to a certain type. The practice of data generalization is often regarded as one of the strategies for reducing data. We need to properly arrange the data in order for it to function correctly when it is imported into Data Mining programs like SPSS and RStudio. In order to determine which of the data set’s independent variables are the most important, we will utilize the T test.
4. Feature Selection: One of the Core Concepts of DM Feature [19-20] selection is one of the core concepts of DM. Feature selection is the process of selecting the most valuable variables from a data set in order to improve the precision and accuracy of DM outputs. Feature selection is one of the most important aspects of DM.
5. Modeling and Experiments: During this stage, there will be a series of experiments that will be performed in order to change the characteristics of the data set. It indicates that the characteristics will be employed in a manner that takes into consideration the influence that they have on the target class. In order to create a Decision Tree prediction model [21-24], we will use the RStudio testing tool to run our experiments. Following the conclusion of the testing, there will be accuracy.

2.2 Flowchart

This is the flow chart of our data mining process:

Fig. 1: Flow Chart

2.3 Model Evaluation

In order to get the data ready for generalization, it is need to make some adjustments to it once it has been uploaded to an Excel sheet. Following that, Excel file is need to be saved. The first set of components to be found was made up of continuous demographic traits, which are comprised of the following: (age, gen- der, children, financial background of family, educational qualification). The second set analyzes the student’s academic achievement by taking into account the grades obtained during the semester. The third group concentrated on social factors that have an impact on performance, such as the advantages and disadvantages associated with one’s place of residence. The third category of criteria that were shown to be the most important was comprised of things like class attendance, gadget use, and materials [25-32] used in class, among other things. The questionnaire has forty questions that together cover more than twenty-four different categories of information.

There are two approaches to making the decision:

1. “critical value” or “critical region” or “rejection region”) approach:

The procedure to follow for testing the validity of a population percentage using a critical value approach hypothesis. The operation is as follows:

- i. Provide an explanation for both the “**null hypothesis**” (H_0) and the “**alter- native hypothesis**” (H_A/H_1).
- ii. Calculate the test statistic:

$$Z = \frac{(P - P_0)}{\sqrt{\frac{P_0(1 - P_0)}{n}}}$$
- iii. Determine the area that is considered crucial.
- iv. Come to a conclusion. Find out if the test statistic is inside the crucial zone. In such case, we may conclude that the null hypothesis is incorrect. If it does not, then the null hypothesis should not be rejected.

For testing $H_0: P_1 = P_2$, some statisticians use the test statistic:

$$Z = \frac{(P_1 - P_2) - 0}{\sqrt{(P(1-P))\left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)}}$$

2. “p-value” approach:

The P-value is the minimal level of significance α at which the null hypothesis is rejected. Alternatively (and this is how I prefer to think of P-values), the P-value is the chance that we would see a more extreme statistic if the null hypothesis were true. If the P-value is low, if $P \leq \alpha$ we reject the null hypothesis H_0 .

2.4 Test

Using this Z, we will locate the Z zone and reject — note that this does not mean reject the region. Following that step, the Z value for each component will be calculated. Minitab will be used to calculate the Z value. During the stage of categorization, the components of the “White Zone” and the “Red Zone” will both be separated out into their respective groups. Following that, the aforementioned file will be imported into RStudio for the purpose of model creation. RStudio [33-35] will also perform other calculations. The model that our manufacturer uses to forecast whether or not students will be happy with their online education.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 T test

Now for different type of indication we will find the value of Z and P.

Table 1: Satisfaction level according to marital status

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Marital Status				
Single	79.31	y1 = 667	n1 = 841	p1 = 0.79 P = 0.804
Married	85.88	y2 = 146	n2 = 170	p2 = 0.86 Z = -2.18

Here in Table 1

$$p_1 = \frac{667}{841} = 0.79$$

$$p_2 = \frac{146}{170} = 0.86$$

$$p = \frac{667 + 146}{841 + 170} = 0.804$$

$$Z = \frac{(0.79 - 0.86) - 0}{\sqrt{(0.804(1 - 0.804))\left(\frac{1}{841} + \frac{1}{170}\right)}} = -2.18$$

Using RStudio we will find the p_1 , p_2 , \hat{p} value for marital status.

```
> xtabs(~ Satisfaction + Marriage_Status, data = d)
      Marriage_Status
Satisfaction Married Single
0         24      174
1        146      667

> crosstabs <- xtabs(~ Satisfaction + Marriage_Status, data = d)
> prop.table(crosstabs,2)
      Marriage_Status
Satisfaction Married  Single
0 0.1411765 0.2068966
1 0.8588235 0.7931034

> 100* prop.table(crosstabs,2)
      Marriage_Status
Satisfaction Married  Single
0 14.11765 20.68966
1 85.88235 79.31034
```

Fig.2: Sample proportion value for marital status using RStudio

Using Mini tab, we will find the Z value for marital status.

Fig.3: Z value for marital status using Mini tab

Fig.4: Comparison marital status with satisfied population

From the Fig. 4 we can observe the level of satisfied population according to their marital status. In table we can see our total respondents were 1011. Among 1011 respondents 667 were single and 146 were married/ divorced. 79.31% of single respondents were satisfied and 85.33% of married/ divorced respondents were satisfied. If Z is more than 1.96 or less than -

1.96, we reject the null hypothesis H0. We definitely reject since -2.18 is in the “red zone,” meaning it is less than -1.96. At the 0.05 level, there is enough evidence to indicate that the two populations differ in their attitudes on marital status in terms of online class satisfaction.

Table 2: Satisfaction level according to age

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Age				
≤ 24	79.03	y ₁ = 573	n ₁ = 725	p ₁ = 0.79
height > 24	83.92	y ₂ = 240	n ₂ = 286	p ₂ = 0.84

Here, in Table 2

$$p_1 = \frac{573}{725} = 0.79$$

$$p_2 = \frac{240}{286} = 0.86$$

$$p = \frac{573 + 240}{725 + 286} = 0.804$$

$$Z = \frac{(0.79 - 0.86) - 0}{\sqrt{(0.804(1 - 0.804))\left(\frac{1}{725} + \frac{1}{286}\right)}} = -1.85$$

Using RStudio we will find the p_1 , p_2 , p^{\wedge} value for marital status.

Using Minitab we will find the Z value for age.

Among the respondents 725 respondents were equal to 24 years or less than 24 years old and 286 respondents were more than 24 years old. 79.03% among equal to 24 years or less than 24 years old and 83.92% among more than 24 years old are satisfied with online education. If Z is larger than 1.96 or less than -1.96, we obviously support the null hypothesis H_0 . This is because -1.85 is in the “white zone,” implying that -1.85 is greater than -1.96.

```
> xtabs(~ Satisfaction + Age, data = d)
      Age
Satisfaction <=24 Yrs >24 Yrs
      0      152      46
      1      573     240
> crosstabs <- xtabs(~ Satisfaction + Age, data = d)
> prop.table(crosstabs,2)
      Age
Satisfaction <=24 Yrs >24 Yrs
      0 0.2096552 0.1608392
      1 0.7903448 0.8391608
> 100* prop.table(crosstabs,2)
      Age
Satisfaction <=24 Yrs >24 Yrs
      0 20.96552 16.08392
      1 79.03448 83.91608
```

Fig.5: Sample proportion value for age using RStudio

Fig.6: Z value for age using Minitab

Fig.7: Comparison age with satisfied population

Table 3: Satisfaction level according to gender

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Gender				
Male	81	$y_1 = 788$	$n_1 = 875$	$p_1 = 0.81$ $P = 0.804$
Female	69	$y_2 = 25$	$n_2 = 36$	$p_2 = 0.69$ $Z = 1.78$

```
> xtabs(~ Satisfaction + Gender, data =d)
      Gender
Satisfaction Female Male
      No       11  187
      Yes       25  788

> crosstabs <- xtabs(~ Satisfaction + Gender, data =d)
> prop.table(crosstabs,2)
      Gender
Satisfaction  Female    Male
      No  0.3055556 0.1917949
      Yes 0.6944444 0.8082051

> 100* prop.table(crosstabs,2)
      Gender
Satisfaction  Female    Male
      No  30.55556 19.17949
      Yes 69.44444 80.82051
```

Fig. 8: Sample proportion value for age using RStudio

Table 3 shows that 875 respondents are male and 81% of them satisfied with online education and 36 respondents are female and 69% of them satisfied with online classes. We clearly supported, since 1.78 falls in the “white zone,” that is, 1.78 is less than 1.96.

Fig. 9: Comparison gender with satisfied population

Table 4: Satisfaction level according to living location

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Living Location				
Dhaka	83	$y_1 = 509$	$n_1 = 615$	$p_1 = 0.83$
Out of Dhaka	77	$y_2 = 304$	$n_2 = 396$	$p_2 = 0.77$

Fig. 10: Comparison living location with satisfied population

Table 4 shows that again 615 respondents are live in Dhaka, from which 83% were satisfied and 396 respondents are live outside of Dhaka, from which 77% were satisfied with online education. If Z is greater than or equal to 1.96, the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. We categorically deny because 2.35 is in the “red zone”, 2.35 is higher than 1.96.

Table 5: Satisfaction level according to family member

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Family Member				
≥ 5	81	$y_1 = 492$	$n_1 = 611$	$p_1 = 0.81$
< 5	80	$y_2 = 321$	$n_2 = 400$	$p_2 = 0.8$

Here we can observe 611 respondents have equal or greater than 5 family member and 81% of them are satisfied with online education. 400 respondents have less than 5 family member and 80% of them are satisfied with online education. If Z is greater than or equal to 1.96, the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. We strongly approve it because 0.39 is in the “white zone,” meaning it is less than 1.96 found in Table 5.

Table 6: Satisfaction level according to parenting students

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Children				
Yes	88	$y_1 = 65$	$n_1 = 74$	$p_1 = 0.88$
No	80	$y_2 = 748$	$n_2 = 937$	$p_2 = 0.8$

In Table 6, 74 respondents have children and 88% of them are satisfied with online education. 937 respondents do not have any children and 80% of them are satisfied with online education. If Z is more than 1.96 or less than -1.96, the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. We strongly support because 1.67 is in the “white zone”, it is less than 1.96.

Table 7: Satisfaction level according to family income

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Family income				
$< 20K$	81	$y_1 = 489$	$n_1 = 601$	$p_1 = 0.81$
$\geq 20K$	79	$y_2 = 324$	$n_2 = 410$	$p_2 = 0.79$

Approximately 601 respondents have less 20-thousand-taka income and 81% of them are satisfied with online education. 410 respondents have equal or more than 20-thousand-taka income and 79% of them are satisfied with online education. If Z is greater than 1.96 or smaller than -1.96, we support the null hypothesis H_0 . We strongly approve since 0.79 is in the “white zone,” meaning it is less than 1.96 found in Table 7.

Table 8: Satisfaction level according to occupation

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Occupation				
Student	78	$y_1 = 507$	$n_1 = 654$	$p_1 = 0.78$
Student + Job	86	$y_2 = 306$	$n_2 = 357$	$p_2 = 0.86$

Table 8 shows that 654 respondents were students and 78% of them are satisfied with online education. 357 respondents were student and job holder and 86% are satisfied with online education. We definitely reject since -3.06 is in the “red zone”, it is less than -1.96.

Table 9: Satisfaction level according to current educational status

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Current Educational Status				
Graduation	80	$y_1 = 718$	$n_1 = 895$	$p_1 = 0.80$
Others Degree	82	$y_2 = 95$	$n_2 = 116$	$p_2 = 0.82$

Table 9 shows that Respondents are doing graduation and 80% of them are satisfied. 116 respondents are doing other courses in online and 82% of them are satisfied with online education. Since -0.51 is more than -1.96, we obviously backed it.

Table 10: Satisfaction level according to type of institution

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Type of institution				
Government	76	$y_1 = 13$	$n_1 = 17$	$p_1 = 0.76$
Private	80	$y_2 = 800$	$n_2 = 994$	$p_2 = 0.8$

Table 10 shows that 17 respondents are doing government jobs and 76% of them satisfied with online education and 994 respondents are doing private jobs and 80% of them satisfied with online classes. Since -0.41 is more than -1.96, we obviously backed it.

Table 11: Satisfaction level according to current year

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Current year				
1 st +2 nd year	84	$y_1 = 292$	$n_1 = 349$	$p_1 = 0.84$
3 rd +4 th year	79	$y_2 = 521$	$n_2 = 664$	$p_2 = 0.79$

349 respondents are in 1st +2nd year and 84% of them are satisfied with online education and 662 respondents are in 3rd

+4th year and 79% of them are satisfied with online education. We clearly supported, since 1.9 falls in the "white zone," that is, 1.9 is smaller than 1.96 found in Table 11.

Table 12: Satisfaction level according to major

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Major				
Science	79	$y_1 = 694$	$n_1 = 873$	$p_1 = 0.79$
Non-science	86	$y_2 = 119$	$n_2 = 138$	$p_2 = 0.86$

From Table 12, 873 respondents are major in science and 79% of them are satisfied with online education and 138 respondents are major in non-science and 86% of them are satisfied with online education. Since -1.93 is bigger than -1.96, we certainly support.

Table 13: Satisfaction level according to department

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Department				
EEE/ETE/ECE	82	$y_1 = 633$	$n_1 = 768$	$p_1 = 0.82$
Others	74	$y_2 = 180$	$n_2 = 243$	$p_2 = 0.74$

From Table 13, 768 respondents are form EEE/ETE/ECE and 82% of them satisfied with online education. 243 respondents are from other department and 74% of them are satisfied with online education. We categorically reject because 2.74 is in the "red zone", 2.74 is bigger than 1.96.

Table 14: Satisfaction level according to CGPA

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
CGPA				
≥ 3	79	$y_1 = 588$	$n_1 = 745$	$p_1 = 0.79$
≤ 2.99	85	$y_2 = 225$	$n_2 = 266$	$p_2 = 0.85$

Table 14 shows that 588 respondents have CGPA equal or higher than 3.00 and 79% of them satisfied with online education. 225 of respondents have CGPA equal or lower than 2.99 and 85% of them satisfied with online education. We plainly reject since -2.12 is in the "red zone", it is less than -1.96.

Table 15: Satisfaction level according to living zone during COVID-19

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Living Zone during COVID-19				
City	83	$y_1 = 443$	$n_1 = 532$	$p_1 = 0.83$
Village	77	$y_2 = 370$	$n_2 = 479$	$p_2 = 0.77$

During COVID-19, 443 respondents are living in city and 83% of them satisfied with online education. 370 respondents are living in village and 77% of them satisfied with online education. We categorically reject since 2.4 is in the "red zone", 2.4 is bigger than 1.96 found in Table 15.

Table 16: Satisfaction level according to online classroom device

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Online classroom Device				
Both Laptop/Desktop and smart phone	81	$y_1 = 191$	$n_1 = 237$	$p_1 = 0.81$ $P = 0.804$
Only smart phone	81	$y_2 = 620$	$n_2 = 768$	$p_2 = 0.81$

Table 16 shows that In case of communication device, 237 respondents have both laptop/desktop and smart phone and 81% of them satisfied with online education. 768 respondents have only smart phone and 81% of them satisfied with online education. We strongly approve because 0 is in the “white zone”, greater than -1.96.

Table 17: Satisfaction level according to internet speed

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Internet speed				
≤ 2 Mbps	81	$y_1 = 555$	$n_1 = 684$	$p_1 = 0.81$
> 2 Mbps	79	$y_2 = 258$	$n_2 = 327$	$p_2 = 0.79$

Table 17 shows that In case of internet speed, 684 respondents have equal or less than 2 mbps internet speed and 81% of them are satisfied with online education. 396 respondents have more than 2 mbps internet speed and 77% of them are satisfied with online education. We clearly support, since 0.75 falls in the “white zone,” that is, 0.75 is smaller than 1.96.

Table 18: Satisfaction level according to social media usage rate

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Social media usage rate				
Daily	81	$y_1 = 650$	$n_1 = 798$	$p_1 = 0.81$
Frequently	79	$y_2 = 131$	$n_2 = 166$	$p_2 = 0.79$

Table 18 shows that 789 respondents are using social media daily and 81% of them are satisfied with online education. 166 respondents are using social media frequently and 79% of them are satisfied with online education. We clearly support, since 0.59 falls in the “white zone,” that is, 0.59 is smaller than 1.96.

Table 19: Satisfaction level according to online class attendance rate

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Online class attendance rate				
Yes	81	$y_1 = 811$	$n_1 = 1001$	$p_1 = 0.81$
No	20	$y_2 = 2$	$n_2 = 10$	$p_2 = 0.2$

Table 19 shows that respondents are attending online classes and 81% of them are satisfied. 10 respondents are not attending online classes and 20% of them are satisfied. We categorically reject since 4.84 is in the “red zone”, it is more than 1.96.

Table 20: Satisfaction level according to online class materials

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Online class materials				
Yes	91	$y_1 = 693$	$n_1 = 758$	$p_1 = 0.91$
No	47	$y_2 = 120$	$n_2 = 253$	$p_2 = 0.47$

Table 20 shows that 758 respondents have useful and class materials and 91% respondents are satisfied with online education. 253 respondents do not have useful materials and 47% respondents are satisfied. We categorically reject because 15.27 is in the “red zone”, larger than 1.96.

Table 21: Satisfaction level according to communication skill enhancement

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Communication skill enhancement				
Yes	88	$y_1 = 724$	$n_1 = 820$	$p_1 = 0.88$
No	47	$y_2 = 89$	$n_2 = 191$	$p_2 = 0.47$

In terms of enhancing communication skills 820 respondents are agreed online education enhance communication skills and 88% of them satisfied with online education. 191 respondents are disagreed online education enhance communication skills and 47% of them satisfied with online education. We categorically reject because 12.86 is in the “red zone” meaning it is greater than 1.96 found in Table 21.

Table 22: Satisfaction level according to suitable video-telephony software for online class platform

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Suitable video-telephony software for online class platform				
Zoom	81	$y_1 = 794$	$n_1 = 976$	$p_1 = 0.81$
Google meet	70	$y_2 = 88$	$n_2 = 125$	$p_2 = 0.7$

Table 22 shows that in context of suitable online class platform, 976 respondents are using Zoom app and 81% of them are satisfied with online education. 125 respondents are using Google meet app and 70% of them are satisfied with online education. We categorically reject because 2.92 is in the “red zone”, 2.92 is bigger than 1.96.

Table 23: Satisfaction level according to suitable online exam evaluation process

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Online exam evaluation process				
Ok	92	$y_1 = 489$	$n_1 = 534$	$p_1 = 0.92$
Not ok	68	$y_2 = 324$	$n_2 = 477$	$p_2 = 0.68$

Table 23 shows that respondents are agreed that online exam process is Ok for evaluation and 92% of them are satisfied. 477 respondents are disagreed and 68% of them satisfied. We categorically deny, because 9.6 is in the “red zone”, it is more than 1.96.

Table 24: Satisfaction level according to recommendation

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Recommendation				
Recommended	87	y1 = 743	n1 = 857	p1 = 0.87
Discouraged	45	y2 = 70	n2 = 154	p2 = 0.7

Table 24 shows that among the respondents 857 were recommended online education and 87% of them are satisfied and 154 were discouraging online education and 45% of them are satisfied with online education. If Z is more than 1.96 or less than -1.96, we reject the null hypothesis H_0 . We categorically reject since 4.89 is in the “red zone,” i.e., 4.89 is bigger than 1.96.

Table 25: Satisfaction level according to overall online education cost

Indications	Satisfied (%)	Number of satisfied participants	Number of participants	T test
Overall online education cost				
Increase	81	y1 = 360	n1 = 445	p1 = 0.81
Decrease/unchanged	80	y2 = 566	n2 = 154	p2 = 0.8

Table 25 shows that respondents are agreed that overall online education increase cost and 81% of them are satisfied. Again 566 respondents are agreed that overall online education decrease/ unchanged and 80% of them are satisfied. We clearly support, since 0.4 falls in the “white zone,” that is, 0.4 is smaller than 1.96.

3.2 Model Creation

This part will discuss how the prediction model was constructed using a Decision tree and how, out of three classifiers, the most accurate one was chosen. In this part of the model creation, we have used R Studio to find out the best classifier for the model.

- **Decision Tree**

Using the Poisson Regression and Crosstab techniques, we were able to identify the relevant features that might create a more accurate prediction model for our data set. The following are the names of chosen variables from the primary data set:

- i. Gender
- ii. Age
- iii. Marriage Status Children Family Member Family Income Division Occupation
- iv. Educational Cost Course
- v. Type of Institution Current Year Major
- vi. Department CGPA
- vii. Online Exam Evaluation Current State
- viii. device Internet speed
- ix. Social Platform Frequency Video-telephony Software Attending Online Class Online Class Accuracy Virtual Class Significance Online Platform
- x. Study Material Collection

3.3 Decision Tree Code

Using the Decision Tree classifier, we utilized these variables to build our prediction model in R Studio. From Fig.11, First, we must load the required libraries for the Decision tree. Without these libraries, it would be impossible to create a flawless model. After importing the data, the dataset had to be called. Every categorical variable must be transformed into factors. Then, the code for drawing the tree is executed

```

1 library(tidyverse)
2 library(rpart)
3 library(rpart.plot)
4
5 library(readr)
6 #setwd("C:/users/old/documents/rd/test")
7 d <- read_csv("ccset.csv")
8
9 fit <- rpart(satisfaction ~
10             Gender
11             + Age
12             + Marriage_Status
13             + Children
14             + Family_Member
15             + Family_Income
16             + Division
17             + Occupation
18             + educational_cost
19             + Course
20             + Type_of_institution
21             + Current_year
22             + Major
23             + Department
24             + CGPA
25             + online_exam_evaluation
26             + Current_state
27             + device
28             + Internet_speed
29             + social_platform_frequency
30             + video_calling
31             + attending_online_class
32             + online_class_accuracy
33             + virtual_class_significance
34             + online_platform
35             + recommendation
36             ,
37             data = d, method = 'class')
38 rpart.plot(fit, extra = 106, under = FALSE,
39            facilen = 10)
40
41
42 head(d)
43 levels(d$satisfaction)=0:1
44 table(d$satisfaction)
45 mymodel <- glm(satisfaction~Gender+Age+Marriage_status+Children+Family_Member+Division+Occupation+Course+Type_of_institution+Current_Year+
46               Major+Department+CGPA+Current_state+device+Internet_speed+social_platform_frequency+video_calling+attending_online_class+
47               Online_class_accuracy+virtual_class_significance+online_platform+online_exam_evaluation+educational_cost+recommendation,
48               family = binomial(link="logit"),data=d)
49 pmodel <- predict(mymodel,d)
50 tab = table(pmodel)
51 sum(diag(tab))/sum(tab)*100
52 table(d$satisfaction)
53 tab
54 sum(diag(tab))/sum(tab)*100
55 table(d$satisfaction)
56 198/(198-813)*100
5428 (Top Level)

```

Fig 11: Code in RStudio for plotting Decision Tree

3.4 Decision Tree Plotting

In the Fig.12, the most crucial variable is ‘Recommend,’ which begins the first node [36]. The second significant variable is ‘Current state’. 85% student will recommend and 15% discourage others. Among discouraged 15% student 7% from Village and 8% from city, then these 7% discouraged village student disagree with online exam 6%. From these 6% ,4% student was running in 1st or 2nd year. In this 1st or 2nd year student 2% from Electrical/Electronics/Communication Engineering student and 2% from another department. This is how a model may be constructed using a decision tree.

Fig.12: Prediction Model using Decision Tree

Here we attempted to calculate Z value for every factors and plot them in Z region. Then we used these dataset in RStudio to develop the prediction model and plot decision tree.

3.5 Influential Factors

Finding factors:

- **Factors in Red zone:** Marital Status, District, Occupation, Department, CGPA, Living Zone during COVID-19, Online class attendance rate, Online class materials, Recommendation, Communication skill enhancement, online exam evaluation process, suitable video-telephony software.
- **Factors in White zone:** Gender, Parent Student, Family member, Age, Family monthly income, Current educational Status, Type of institution, Current year, Major, Online class Device, Internet Speed, Social media usage rate, overall online education cost.

From this factor we can easily understand that which factors are needed to be focused for developing institutional satisfactorily in an online class.

3.6 Accuracy of Decision Tree

Using decision tree, we can calculate accuracy in RStudio. System accuracy 86.34

```
      0  1
FALSE 112 63
TRUE  68 716
> sum(diag(tab))/sum(tab)*100
[1] 86.33994
> |
```

Fig.13: Proposed model accuracy

4. Conclusion

Before Covid-19, online classes were very unfamiliar in our country. But during this time, educational institutions are forced to take online classes. So online classes were new to almost everyone. Although that online class was prevalent abroad, it was not in our country. The subject was new to almost everyone. Overcoming various obstacles, everyone has set foot on this new horizon. In 2020, it is very inaccessible [37], but in 2022, everyone has adapted to this online class. However, they did not get used to the online class as much as the offline class. As a result, the purpose of this research is to highlight critical factors in order to break the cycle of inertia. Here, 1011 students have expressed their views about online [38-40] class experience in the questionnaires'. We have worked with those QA and found some basic factors. These factors categorized by T test. Finally, found some factors those are able to meet student's satisfactory level and need to be focused. The decision tree was drawn using data mining techniques, and the system accuracy was 86.34 percent. Since this online system is new to us, the educational institution can make online education [41-42] fruitful by giving importance to these issues if they want. It will also inspire students towards online learning. Many educational activities can be done parallelly in online as well as offline. In this digital age, digital devices are in everyone's hands, so online education will also be in the path of education lovers. It could be the opportunity for dropout and working students. Improving these factors, benefits of online learning can be enjoyed.

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